

A Report on Reproducibility of "Detecting Fake News from News Title and Body: A Reproducibility Study"

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1 INTRODUCTION

This report is about the reproducibility of "*Textual Characteristics of News Title and Body to Detect Fake News: A Reproducibility Study*" by Anu Shrestha and Francesca Spezzano published in 2021. The paper is a replication of Horne and Adali's study published in 2017 that focuses on analyzing fake news via title and body texts. The reproducibility study analyzes fake news titles and bodies extracted from GossipCop, PolitiFact, and BuzzFeed News datasets and focuses on three linguistic feature clusters: stylistic, psychological, and complexity features. The authors used the same experimental setup as Horne and Adali [1] and they incorporated larger datasets into their experiment. In our study, we adhere to the same experimental design and methodologies as described in the paper by Shrestha and Spezzano [2] while maintaining the objective of the study in our attempt to replicate the results.

While the code and the datasets were provided and experimental setup and workflow were described thoroughly by the authors, it was rather challenging to replicate the results. The authors conducted the study before 2021, and many news articles that are used in each dataset were no longer available online, having since been moved or deleted. Therefore the primary obstacle in reproducing the results in this paper stems from the unavailability of the data. Additionally, one of the tools used in the reproducibility study named LIWC is a non-open source tool, therefore, we were required to get access to the LIWC dictionary beforehand. Despite these challenges, we proceeded with the remaining available data and conducted the analysis accordingly.

2 REPLICATION PROCESS

The research goal of the paper by Horne and Adali and the reproducibility study conducted by Shrestha and Spezzano is to explore the differences between fake and real news content based on linguistic features. With the aim to reproduce the findings of the former study [2], Shrestha and Spezzano hypothesized that fake news content significantly differs from real news content in terms of linguistic features; namely, stylistic, psychological and complexity features. Defined similarly to Horne and Adali's study, the authors of the reproducibility study considered stylistic features on the basis of textual functionality involving different grammatical elements, psychological features with regards to emotions expressed through the text and complexity features in terms of how easily the text can be read and understood by the reader. The authors tested these assumptions in larger datasets integrating a wider array of features and measures by employing a similar experimental design and methodologies.

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In this report, our objective was to follow the experimental design and methodologies employed by Shrestha and Spezzano. The study has been structured into five steps where the first step focuses on data preparation, the second step implements feature extraction, the third step involves bringing all features together, the fourth step revolves around statistical evaluation and finally the fifth step is about classification and reproducing the results in the paper. Following these steps, we utilized the code and dataset provided by the authors, however, we encountered a challenge during the data preparation stage, as the original data that was provided was no longer fully accessible. To address this issue, we incorporated additional preprocessing into the analysis.

2.1 Data Acquisition and Preprocessing

In order to acquire the data we used the instructions provided by the authors including a web-scraping tool and a number of links to articles. These links are already annotated as either fake or real news articles. Upon running the web-crawler on the links we got very messy datasets with many articles being deleted, behind paywalls, moved internally or similar. In many instances, the tool failed and copied different parts of the website that had nothing to do with the news article, including again error messages, login pages, paywalls, or similar. We decided to proceed to the next steps only after thoroughly cleaning the datasets and removing erroneous entries. Since all of these parts had to be done semi-manually by detecting the potential errors in the texts, it is not possible to state that the data is entirely error-free, as detecting all errors in large datasets involving over 18.000 entries poses challenges. This might of course negatively impact the results. As can be seen in the tables below, this reduced the size of the datasets. When all of the unusable news were removed from the datasets, a total number of 664 news for PolitiFact, 1.511 news for BuzzFeed News, and 18.573 news for GossipCop datasets were acquired as presented in Table 2.

Data Source	Count		
	#Total	#Real	#Fake
BuzzFeed News	1.561	299	1.262
PolitiFact	838	378	460
GossipCop	19.759	4.734	15.025

Table 1. Dataset - Reproducibility Study by Shrestha and Spezzano [2]

Data Source	Count		
	#Total	#Real	#Fake
BuzzFeed News	1.511	279	1.232
PolitiFact	664	303	361
GossipCop	18.573	4.427	14.146

Table 2. Dataset - Our Replication

2.2 Feature Extraction

The reproducibility study incorporates similar features as in the paper by Horne and Adali. Table 3 shows the summary of the tools and measures that are used in the reproducibility study for each of the linguistic feature clusters.

In the original paper, a GitHub repository was referenced, containing the necessary code for feature extraction. However, the provided code was not immediately executable. To perform feature extraction, we needed to run four Jupyter notebooks, in addition to several Python scripts for various calculations. After installing all documented necessary packages, further packages had to be installed, but due to the lack of documentation, it cannot be ensured that the exact same versions were used.

In the first step, we aimed to calculate LIWC features. Due to the unavailability of the correct LIWC tool software version, we had to resort to a LIWC dictionary file obtained with some luck and simulate the software tool using the provided sample code. Similar adjustments were needed in all subsequent steps, such as correcting paths referring to a

Google Colab account to which we had no access or addressing inconsistencies in file names. As a result, features were saved in six files for each dataset, covering news body text and titles.

The second notebook computed the remaining features. Here, we had to manually search for and include another dictionary file for "Emotion Intensity", and again, it cannot be guaranteed that the correct version was used. This step had a long runtime of several hours, possibly due to inefficient programming, but we did not develop an improved version.

The next step involved merging the files for each dataset, body text and titles. Various checks were performed to ensure the alignment of data quantities, and only necessary data were stored. Due to the lack of clearly documented column labels, manual adjustments were necessary to make this part functional.

The feature extraction concluded with a notebook on statistical tests. Here, the statistical significance of the features was determined, and tables for the report were created. Unfortunately, this process was not entirely completed, as the column labels in the data frames did not exactly match those in the report. Thus, additional interventions were necessary to make the values comparable.

Stylistic Features	Psychological Features	Complexity Features
LIWC	LIWC	Flesh Kincaid Grade Level (FK)
Python NTLK Part of Speech tagger (POS)	VADER	Gunning Fog Index (GI)
	Emotion Intensity Lexicon (NRC-EIL)	Simple Measure of Gobbledygook Index (SMOG)
		Type Token Ratio (TTK)

Table 3. Summary of Linguistic Measures and Tools

2.3 Selected Features

In the reproducibility study the authors stated that they had 68 features in total and they applied ANOVA and Wilcoxon rank-sum tests for their analyses which are also used by Horne and Adali to perform the selection of features.

We followed the authors' approach and computed the features via the tools they used according to the code that they provided. The tables show the comparison between their and our results for the features of the body texts and titles. All differences are statistically significant. We used the same notation by the authors to present whether the feature value differences between fake and real news were greater as 'R>F' or 'F>R'. The blank spaces indicate that there aren't any statistically significant outcomes.

On the left side, you can see the results of the original study, and on the right are our results. It is evident that we achieved significantly fewer statistically significant differences. Some differences even had opposite results, as indicated by the underlined results in the corresponding tables.

Surprisingly, we obtained relatively decent results for the features of the news body texts. The only notable difference occurred in the Gunning Fog Index (GI) feature, which produced an opposing result in the BuzzFeed dataset. More noticeable distinctions were observed in the features related to the news titles.

The absence of data may have a more substantial impact on short texts, such as news titles. In contrast, news body texts appear to be somewhat more robust in this regard.

Body Features - Reproducibility Study by Shrestha and Spezzano [2]

Features	PolitiFact	BuzzFeed	GossipCop	Features	PolitiFact	BuzzFeed	GossipCop
allPunc	R>F	R>F	R>F	analytic	F>R	R>F	R>F
exclam	F>R	F>R	F>R	quote	F>R	R>F	F>R
tone	R>F	R>F	R>F	WC	R>F	R>F	R>F
WPS		R>F	R>F	affect		F>R	R>F
affil	R>F			cause		F>R	F>R
certain		F>R	F>R	all_caps	R>F	R>F	R>F
differ	R>F	F>R	F>R	discrep	R>F	F>R	F>R
FK		R>F		focusfuture		F>R	F>R
GI		R>F	F>R	i		R>F	R>F
insight		F>R		interro		R>F	
leisure	F>R		R>F	TTR	F>R	F>R	
money	R>F			negate		F>R	R>F
netspeak			R>F	JJ	R>F	R>F	R>F
RB	R>F	R>F		CD	R>F	R>F	R>F
DT	R>F	R>F	R>F	UH	R>F		
NN	R>F	R>F	R>F	NNP	R>F	R>F	R>F
PRP	R>F	R>F	R>F	PRP\$	R>F	R>F	
VBD	R>F	R>F	R>F	VBG	R>F	R>F	
VBN	R>F	R>F		VBP	R>F	R>F	R>F
VBZ	R>F	R>F		VB	R>F	R>F	R>F
WP	R>F	R>F	R>F	WDT	R>F	R>F	R>F
per_stop	F>R	F>R	F>R	power		R>F	R>F
quant	R>F			reliq	F>R	F>R	
reward			R>F	risk		F>R	
sheshe	F>R		F>R	SMOG		R>F	F>R
swear	F>R	F>R		tentant		F>R	F>R
we	R>F		R>F	avg_wlen		R>F	
work	R>F			you	R>F	F>R	R>F
compare		R>F		focuspast		F>R	F>R
neg	F>R	F>R	F>R	surprise	F>R		
disgust	F>R	F>R		negemo	F>R	F>R	
pos	R>F			fear	F>R		
posemo	R>F			anx	F>R	F>R	
sadness	F>R	F>R	F>R	anger		F>R	F>R
trust			F>R	joy		F>R	F>R

Body Features - Our Replication

Features	PolitiFact	BuzzFeed	GossipCop	Features	PolitiFact	BuzzFeed	GossipCop
allPunc				analytic			
exclam				quote			
tone				WC	R>F		R>F
WPS				affect			
affil				cause			
certain				all_caps	R>F		R>F
differ				discrep			
FK		R>F		focusfuture			R>F
GI	F>R	<u>F>R</u>	F>R	i			
insight				interrog			
leisure				TTR			
money				negate			
netspeak				JJ	R>F		R>F
RB	R>F	R>F		CD	R>F		R>F
DT	R>F	R>F	R>F	UH	R>F		
NN	R>F	R>F	R>F	NNP	R>F		R>F
PRP	R>F	R>F	R>F	PRP\$	R>F		R>F
VBD	R>F	R>F		VBG	R>F		R>F
VBN	R>F	R>F		VBP	R>F		R>F
VBZ	R>F	R>F		VB	R>F		R>F
WP	R>F	R>F		WDT	R>F		R>F
per_stop		F>R	F>R	power			
quant				reliq			
reward				risk			
sheshe				SMOG			R>F
swear				tentant			
we				avg_wlen			R>F
work				you			
compare				focuspast			
neg	F>R	F>R	F>R	surprise	F>R		
disgust	F>R	F>R		negemo	F>R		
pos	R>F			fear	F>R		
posemo	R>F			anx	F>R		
sadness	F>R	F>R	F>R	anger			F>R
trust	R>F		F>R	joy			

Title Features - Reproducibility Study by Shrestha and Spezzano [2]

Features	PolitiFact	BuzzFeed	GossipCop	Features	PolitiFact	BuzzFeed	GossipCop
WC	F>R	F>R		avg_wlen	R>F	R>F	F>R
quote	F>R	F>R	F>R	allPunc	R>F		F>R
exclam	F>R	F>R	F>R	tone	R>F	R>F	
WPS	F>R	F>R	R>F	affect	F>R	R>F	
affil			F>R	compare	F>R	R>F	
differ			F>R	discrep	F>R	F>R	
focusfuture	F>R		F>R	focuspast	F>R	F>R	
insight		F>R		interrog			R>F
leisure			R>F	TTR	F>R		F>R
money		R>F		negate			F>R
netspeak	R>F		R>F	JJ	R>F		R>F
UH			F>R	GI	F>R		F>R
FK	F>R		F>R	SMOG	F>R		F>R
analytic		R>F	R>F	all_caps	F>R	F>R	
NN	R>F	R>F	R>F	NNP	F>R	F>R	
PRP	F>R	F>R	R>F	PRP\$	F>R	F>R	
DT			R>F	RB	F>R	F>R	
VBD	F>R			VBG	F>R	F>R	
VBN	F>R			VBP	F>R	F>R	
VBZ	F>R	R>F		VB	F>R	F>R	
WP		F>R		per_stop	F>R	F>R	
quant			R>F	reliq	F>R		F>R
reward			R>F	risk			F>R
work	R>F	R>F		i			R>F
you			R>F	shehe	F>R	F>R	
CD			R>F	fear	F>R	F>R	
neg	F>R	F>R	F>R	sadness	F>R	F>R	
surprise	F>R	R>F		anger	F>R	F>R	
negemo	F>R		F>R	trust	R>F		R>F
disgust	F>R	F>R	F>R	pos			R>F
posemo			R>F	anx			F>R
joy			R>F				

Title Features - Our Replication

Features	PolitiFact	BuzzFeed	GossipCop	Features	PolitiFact	BuzzFeed	GossipCop
WC	<u>R>F</u>	<u>R>F</u>		avg_wlen		R>F	F>R
quote				allPunc			
exclam				tone			
WPS				affect			
affil				compare			
differ				discrep			
focusfuture		R>F	<u>R>F</u>	focuspast			
insight				interrog			
leisure				TTR			
money				negate			
netspeak				JJ	R>F		R>F
UH	R>F		F>R	GI	F>R		F>R
FK		R>F		SMOG	R>F		R>F
analytic				all_caps	R>F		R>F
NN	R>F	R>F		NNP	R>F		R>F
PRP	R>F	R>F		PRP\$	R>F		R>F
DT	R>F	R>F	R>F	RB	R>F		F>R
VBD	R>F	R>F		VBG	R>F		F>R
VBN	R>F	R>F		VBP	R>F		F>R
VBZ	R>F	R>F		VB	R>F		F>R
WP	R>F	R>F		per_stop		F>R	F>R
quant		<u>R>F</u>		reliq			
reward				risk			
work				i			
you				shehe			
CD	R>F	R>F	R>F	fear	F>R	F>R	
neg	F>R	F>R	F>R	sadness	F>R	F>R	
surprise	F>R		F>R	anger	F>R		F>R
negemo				trust	R>F		R>F
disgust	F>R	F>R	F>R	pos	R>F		R>F
posemo				anx			
joy			R>F				

2.4 Classification

We ran the same classifiers as the authors of the original study, which are Linear Support vector machines, random forests and Logistic regression. The authors compute multiple metrics in their implementation but only report Average Precision (**AvgP**) and Area under ROC Curve (**AUROC**). They do not explain their choice of metrics. Since it can be argued that making a false negative error is more impactful and harmful than making a false positive (when considering fake news as the 1-class), the recall/sensitivity might be the most interesting metric on this dataset. One could also

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consider using a variant of the F_β metric to weight recall and precision. We decided to consider the F_β metric with $\beta = 2$ in addition to the aforementioned AUROC and AvgP.

Features	PolitiFact			BuzzFeedNews			GossipCop		
	AUROC	AvgP	F_β	AUROC	AvgP	F_β	AUROC	AvgP	F_β
News body (SVM)	0.580	0.502	0.671	0.602	0.253	0.152	0.571	0.289	0.172
News body (LR)	0.819	0.775	0.726	0.662	0.304	0.509	0.633	0.345	0.545
News body (RF)	0.857	0.820	0.753	0.712	0.350	0.043	0.727	0.541	0.290
News Title (SVM)	0.838	0.822	0.749	0.797	0.442	0.624	0.633	0.345	0.442
News Title (LR)	0.829	0.809	0.725	0.799	0.452	0.624	0.636	0.347	0.529
News Title (RF)	0.828	0.810	0.741	0.802	0.407	0.137	0.688	0.455	0.202

Table 4. Performance of different classifiers on the three considered datasets, news body and title evaluated separately. Reported metrics are Average Precision and Area under ROC-Curve. The best-performing classifier on each dataset between text and title is bold.

These results largely match the findings of Shrestha and Spezzano, there are however a few deviations. The best-performing classifiers on the news titles were in our results no longer just random forests, but instead, the best classifiers varied. However, the variance in metrics was small and random forests still gave good results. The difference between our results and their reported results was in general small and on most datasets our metrics were slightly worse. This can largely be put down to the degradation of the datasets due to time, see the aforementioned problems with acquiring the datasets. Figure 3 shows the difference between reported and original values. It is obvious that the largest negative differences are on the re-generated (and thus degraded) datasets.

Fig. 3. Difference in results between replication and original. Reported values are *metric value replicated by us minus metric value reported by Shrestha and Spezzano*.

While the performance of the classifiers regarding AUROC and Average precision led to authors to conclude that the Random Forest ensemble classifier was the most well-suited for this task, the F_β scores paint a different picture. Logistic regression always achieved either the highest F_β score or scored within 5% of the best-performing classifier. In contrast, random forests performed very poorly on some of the tasks. Thus, we need to again question the authors' choice of metrics to evaluate performance.

3 CONCLUSION AND LIMITATIONS

We found that classifying news articles into real and fake news based on stylistic, psychological and complexity features is to an extent possible. Based on the F_β metric with $\beta = 2$ to favour recall over precision, the best-performing classifier was Logistic regression, outperforming Random Forests and Linear SVMs. The results were similar when classifying based on text features vs. title features. This differs from the results of Shrestha and Spezzano, who gave Random Forests as the best classifier based on the AUROC and Average Precision metrics.

Regarding the reproducibility limitations, it is possible to mention that the primary issue was the missing data as some of the links that are included in the study's datasets are no longer available therefore we excluded them from our analysis. When we consider the missing news, it is not possible to replicate the exact dataset analyzed in the actual study and the original study's exact numbers are not reproducible due to the changes in the data sources. Despite this, we did manage to largely confirm their findings. Future studies providing the study data as open source should consider providing the texts instead of the links to the news sources as the links and the website contents can be modified or simply removed. We do however acknowledge that this might not always be possible due to copyright issues. Furthermore, the authors didn't provide explicit information on how they conducted the preprocessing of their data, which also posed a challenge for us, as we were unable to compare their datasets with ours.

While the dataset and the code for this study are provided by the authors, usage of non-open source tools like LIWC is a limitation for the reproducibility of the study as it could be difficult for other researchers to replicate the results if they don't have access to the paid sources.

Minor faults were found in the implementation of the classification tests. While the authors state that they use the most significant features up to the square root of the total number of features, their implementations selects 0.8 times the square root of total features. They do not offer an explanation for this discrepancy.

Finally, we would like to mention an important aspect of the data selection process. It is important to address the question of whether there was any selection bias in collecting the data which could impact the results. We don't have any information regarding the motivation of authors for choosing the news from the stated data sources or the news that is chosen from such data sources for this study. We would like to conclude that it is important that authors provide more information regarding their data selection processes to enhance transparency and facilitate reproducibility.

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